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INVASION OF FOREIGN REALITY SHOWS AND ADVENT OF CELEBRITY REALITY T.V SHOWS ON INDIAN SATELLITE TELEVISION.

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Abstract:

This research paper talks about how foreign reality shows held foot in India and how celebrity culture started to follow even on Indian reality shows.

Introduction:

Indian satellite channels were opened for foreign channels and their serials only after 1992, till then DOORDARSHAN had the monopoly over the Indian television viewing and Indian audience loved shows like HUMLOG, RAMAYAN, MAHABHARAT, MERI AWAAZ SUNO, TOL MOL KE BOL, SAAP SIDHI etc, but as the result of urbanisation and modernisation with the help of liberalisation, many cities came into existence like Pune, Nashik, Surat, Ahmedabad, Gurgaon, Noida etc where industrialisation lead to attraction of labours from other underdeveloped states of the country, the result was change of taste not only in standard of living but also standard in seeing , way of thinking , now people saved only to spend in present and not in future that was primary reason for the existence of mall culture. Some where i give credit to foreign channels invading Indian satellite channels and shows, this triggered a new chapter in Indian communication and broad casting history as these foreign channels not only blended in Indian culture but also modified their content to suit Indian audiences.

To consider the popular resonance of reality TV shows in India is therefore, inevitably, a discussion of the popularity of reality TV formats, which represents one of the growing sectors of trade in the transnational television industry. But the trade in television formats is also an offshoot of the globalization of the television industry itself. End of public broadcasting, privatization of airwaves and deregulation of markets, in keeping with pro-market, neo-liberal policies adopted by nation-states across the world, have led to an increasing flow of capital (Moran, 1998).

Example:

The adaptation of who wants to be a millionaire as KAUN BANEGA CROREPATI (popularly known as KBC) in India was first suggested by the Hongkong based head of Asia Pacific programming for star TV , a subsidiary of news corporation, who sent a video of the original programme to Bombay, today Mumbai. Three staff from celedor U.k were seconded to India to train the local production team and later a team of four from India were sent to U.s.a for further familiarisation with the concept. Still it was a local star tv executive who made the decision to appoint the local movie cult hero Amitabh Bachhan as its compare , the local question were designed which included the blend of Indian culture as well covered all streams of life whether Indian or global.

The star tv network India wanted to take off in Indian market and k.b.c was perfect product to be introduced in Indian market and Indian viewers and helped them transition from a tag of foreign English language programme showing shows like bay watch and other American shows in india to regional hindi entertainment oriented channels, giving tough fight to Indian channels zee and sony.(sanjeev Sharma,2014)

And, in a relatively short span of two decades (1990 to 2010) television has emerged as an immensely lucrative sector in the Indian media and entertainment (M& E) industries – overtaking (in 2002) the famed goliath of Bollywood or Hindi commercial film industry 1) (Singh, 2008)

that churns out films and profits at stupendous rates to become the leader in the M&E industry. The overall television industry in India, which accounts for 329 billion rupees, is nearly half (45%) of the M&E space, which is valued at 728 billion rupees (Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry-KPMG report [FICCI-KPMG], 2012). With a reach of 126 million households connected to a 24X7 C&S television networks, out of a total of 148 million TV owning household (Television Audience Measurement [TAM], 2012),⁴ the television universe in India is the third largest market in the world today, after the United States and China (Hindustan Times, 2007). 2) (lauhona ganguly,2012)

still our television industry is evolving, every channel whether Indian or foreign specially foreign were experimenting with different genres of television show that portrays reality in particular.

objectives:

1. To understand how foreign reality shows are gaining ground on Indian television.
2. To understand the Indian celebrity impact on Indian audience.

The different genres that foreign reality shows experimented are as follows

1. **Special living environment:** contestants are taken in a special environment to compete. Example: fear factor, survivors, amazing race, i am a celebrity, save me from this jungle, man v/s wild.
2. **Soap-opera style:** like a talk show oprah winfrey show
3. **Celebrity reality shows :** reality shows with celebrities, examples: dancing with the stars, the simple life, big brother.
4. **Court shows:**
5. **Dating based reality shows:** reality shows that gave a platform for dating men and women on air. Example: for love or for money, perfect match new York.
6. **Job search:** shows that take live interviews on channels. Example: the apprentice, hell's kitchen etc
7. **Sports reality shows/ adventure / fear :** that reality shows which checks the vigour and valour of contestants. Example: fear factor, who dare win, minute to win it
8. **Make over and renovation:** reality shows that talked about make over stories, whether of an individual or house make over.
9. **Social experiments:** a relatively new genre of reality television, interaction with certain group of society. Example: wife swap, teen pregnancy, my big fat obnoxious fiancé.
10. **Hidden cameras:** these reality show captures emotions and reactions in natural surroundings like just for laugh gags, America's funniest videos.
11. **Super natural and para normal.:** the reality show which talked about super natural powers. Examples: ripley's believe it or not.
12. **Talent hunts:** the show which provided platform for talented people to showcase their talents. Example: American idol, America's got talent etc.

To consider the popular resonance of reality TV shows in India is therefore, inevitably, a discussion of the popularity of reality TV formats, which represents one of the growing sectors of trade in the transnational television industry. But the trade in television formats is also an offshoot of the globalization of the television industry itself. End of public broadcasting, privatization of airwaves and deregulation of markets, in keeping with pro-market, neo-liberal policies adopted by nation-states across the world, have led to an increasing flow of capital (Moran, 1998). But flow of global capital and introduction of new industrial and competitive strategies (like importing formats) and sets different norms for cultural production, making it necessary for all other networks to compete hard to gain momentum in the eyes of viewers (including Zee, a domestic network or Doordarshan, the state broadcaster) to respond by emulating the strategy, filling the prime time with reality TV shows (either from licensed formats or imitated versions).

The reality shows that comes on Indian foreign channels like **AXN**

Reality Series/Game Shows.

- American Ninja Warrior
- Bloopers
- Caught on Camera
- Caught Red Handed
- Criss Angel Mindfreak
- Destination Truth
- Minute to Win It
- Most Shocking
- Ripley's Believe It or Not!
- So You Think You Can Dance
- The Amazing Race
- The Voice (U.S.)
- The X Factor (U.S.)
- Top 20 Countdown
- Top Chef Masters
- Top Gear
- Wipeout
- Wipeout Australia
- World's Wildest Police Videos
- Scare Tactics.

(SOURCE Axn website: axn.com)

Reality show on **star world**

1. America's got talent
2. American idol
3. Are you smarter than 5 th grader
4. Bachlорrate
5. Australian master chef
6. Apprentice
7. America's next top model

Reality shows on **zee cafe**

1. America's Funniest Home Videos
2. America's Got Talent
3. Just for Laughs: Gags

4. The Ellen DeGeneres Show'
5. E! News
6. "American Idol (season 13)"

Most of reality tv in india are just the adoption of the above western formats or from eastern countries, Indian channels do take license from such show and others are inspired from the same.

Some Indian reality shows which are copied straight by taking licence from foreign shows.

- 1) "Kaun banega crorepati" licensed version of "who wants to be a millionaire"
- 2) "Indian idol" licensed version of "pop idol"
- 3) "India's got talent" licensed version of "Britain's got talent."
- 4) "bigg boss" licensed version of "big brother"
- 5) "master chef India" licensed version of "master chef australia"
- 6) "khatron ke khiladi" licensed version of "fear factor"
- 7) "mere khwaabo ki mallika" licensed version of "bachelorette"
- 8) "Jhalak dikhla jaa" licensed version of "dancing with the stars"
- 9) "kya aap paanchvi class se tezz hai" licensed version of "Are you smarter than 5 th grader"
- 10) "kamjor kadi kaun" licensed version of "weakest link"
- 11) "sachh ka samna" licensed version of "moment of truth"
- 12) "dus ka dum" licensed version of "power of ten"
- 13) "x factor India" licensed version of "x factor America"

Some Indian reality show inspired from foreign formats without licence.

1. Roadies
2. Splitsvilla
3. Indian makeover
4. Big fat Indian wedding
5. Dance India dance
6. Just dance
7. Mtv bakra
8. Saare ga ma pa
9. Comedy nights with kapil
10. Nachh baliye
11. India ka best dramebaaz
12. Entertainment ke liye kuchh bhi karega.
13. swayamvar

But again globalisation should be the main factor for discussion of the popularity of the reality shows format which has suddenly caught attentions of Indian viewers. basically this genre is untouched genre in Indian television industry, liberalisation in 1991-92 and its action like public broadcasting coming to an end, deregulation in market allowing foreign competitors to compete with domestic one's not only increased money capital in India but also the growth of transnational Indian television industry.

In india various tv satellite channels are either home owned or private or venture of both like door darshan and zee tv formed Indian public and private channels while star tv, sony, colors, etc are either venture with global media or conglomerates. This flow of capital became very useful in two ways 1) provides finance to compete in competitive tv market.2) provides finance to makers of new and creative shows to attract more viewers for the channel.

Also it has allowed a flow of professional ethics, sharing of know-how, creative and commercial choices with Indian television producer who have turned towards western market for successful adaptation for those formats which are hit in foreign countries, just hoping that it will also be a instant success in Indian market too. The biggest plus point for Indian

channel producers were able to attract global media companies like ‘endemol’, ‘fremantle’, ‘celedor’ etc which had experience of successfully handling western reality shows like ‘who wants to be a millionaire’, big brother, pop idol, etc. Were roped in by Indian channels to replicate tried and tested ideas. And it wasn’t a bad deal for foreign media companies to venture in India either, as India provided vast television market and an opportunity to produce a variety of their formats into Hindi language network or regional network.

No wonder for Indian audience, this was some thing new apart from fiction show, like “kahani ghar ghar ki”, “kasauti zindagi ki”, “kyonki saas bhi bahu thi”etc but for producers it was less risky as the formats were already tasted the success abroad plus Indian producers allowed local cultural attributes or desi tadka to be mixed with the foreign format, gave a perfect blend and achievement for Indian reality shows which not only changed the face of Indian television but also increased revenue and employment in the country.

It gave both Indian channels like d.d , sahara, zee etc to bring this change in their channel and bring desi reality shows to maintain tv space and Indian audience.(moran,1998,lauhana ganguly, 2012).

The top five foreign reality shows that inspire me.

1. **The biggest loser:** tag line is “ the more you lose, the more you win”
This show inspires, motivates, develop self confidence, promote healthy living, dedication, and honesty to one self. The theme of this reality show revolve around contestants who are bulky in weights and those who sheds or reduce the maximum weight will become the biggest loser and wins the prize. this show not only help the participants to get rid of extra fat on them but also helps them to develop fighting spirit , healthy life style in Americans etc (season 15, September 2013).
2. **The amazing race:** the theme is a treasure hunt that is played across cities and in different continents, involving 12-13 pairs or group and who so ever reach the destination first is declared the winner, what i liked about the show is self confidence, willingness to move forward, courage to push yourself to certain limits, desire to win, team work, dedication, come out as a stronger individual, ready to face any obstacle etc. These contestants fights, argue, crib and sometime cheat also but they are full of emotions and feelings that is experienced by any one.
3. **America’s got talent:** the theme is to provide a platform to amateur performers, hidden talent, and popularity for songs, music, dance, comedy, and other entertainment style. The plus point of this show is it makes a common man- a celebrity who is not only won the heart of judges by his best performance but also been able to attract the audiences vote. This show proves hard work, perseverance, belief in self, and passion for success.
4. **Extreme makeover:** home edition:
this reality show helps those who have lost their homes to natural disasters or mishaps or lost a family member. the show helps to address the problems faced in American society and how they face it as a family. It inspires faith, happiness, hope, courage to move on, never say die attitude and promotes thinking about others in time of their needs.
5. **Little people, big world:** this is a unique show where they highlight all the difficulties and sufferings that a person who is a dwarf has to face in his normal living and around his surroundings. This show inspires me to face challenge being a handicap myself, self confidence, positive attitude, never give up also make other’s life happy too.

Top five foreign reality shows that are culturally demoralising for the society.

1. **Big brother:** big brother is a reality show where 12-14 contestants live in a house away from family for three months with no communication with the loved ones. The bad thing about this show is that it promotes sex, nudity, drinking, smoking, flirting, back biting and excess voyeurism. Though this show is not telecasted in India but the uncensored scenes are available on social networking sites like YouTube, twitter, face book. Who knows these shows get permission to be shown on Indian channels.

2. **16 and Pregnant:** is an American reality television series that debuted June 11, 2009, on MTV. It follows the stories of pregnant teenage girls who are studying in high schools dealing with the hardships of teenage pregnancy.
3. **Wife swap:** is an American reality television program that was first broadcasted on the ABC network in 2004. In the program, two families, having different social classes and lifestyles, swap wives/mothers – and sometimes husbands – more than two weeks. The program deliberately swap wives with dramatically lifestyles, such as a troubled wife swapping with a fastidiously clean one, documenting the cultural and social differences that the two families discover with the new family member but The swapped couples do not have sex.
4. **America's next top model:** is an American reality show which provides contestants a chance to become model but contestants are lead into an embarrassing scenarios far outside the real-life modeling. One scenario highlighting when two final contestants were made to wear bikinis so skimpy that the producers had to blur out one finalist butt cheeks and a cheap sexual mud fight.
5. **The Moment of Truth :** the moment of truth is an American game show based on the Colombian Nada más que la verdad format ("Nothing More than the Truth"). Contestants answer a series of 21 increasingly personal and embarrassing questions after testing by polygraph machine, to receive cash prizes. One such question asked is that whether she believed her father had any sexual relations as an adult with a minor. She said she felt he did, and polygraph or the lie detector determined her truth and was declared winner for the grand prize.

Unlike previous forms of television programming, this genre features “real” people on television such as news programs or talk shows, modern reality-based television programming features non professional and non camera centric actors in an unscripted and non scribbled program (Andrejevic, 2002). Audiences have been attracted to something called the “real” characters on news programs, talk shows, documentaries, and re-enactment shows on television for many decades. People have enjoyed reality-based programs on shows such as Candid Camera in the 1940s, The American Family in the 1970s, COPS in the 1980s, and MTV's The Real World in the 1990s. It was not until the early 21st century, however, that reality-based television shows gained mainstream fame with lots of popularity and notoriety with both networks and audiences (Andrejevic, 2002; Leone et al., 2006).

The first sub-genre of reality programs to air on television was with the cameras called hidden camera shows. America's oldest reality show, Candid Camera, ran from 1948 to 2004 (Bratich, 2006). The show played pranks on unsuspecting people. According to Bratich (2006), the sub-genre of hidden camera program interrupts and introspects different aspects of people's everyday lives to not only test people's gullibility, but also their extensible limits. Audiences get to enjoy seeing unsuspecting subjects' fear (Fear Factor), sexual desire (Women Behaving Badly), and hospitality (Damage Control) levels, and celebrities' tolerance levels (Punk'd). Beyond pleasure, Bratich (2006) found that hidden camera shows are also learning tools to test people's tolerance with others living in society. ABC's What Would You Do? is a prime example of a show used to expose intolerance and break barriers to discuss the behaviour of unsuspecting subjects on hidden camera. On MTV's Boiling Point, unaware participants who can maintain calm while being subjected to the intolerable antics of rude/alooof service workers or crazy blind dates win monetary rewards for their patience. (Bratich, 2006).

It is common belief in foreign countries reality television is an attractive medium to foster and garner parasocial relationships. Past research and many current research shows that spectators are more likely to form parasocial relationships with media figures or role models than with fictional soap opera actors. Through reality television consumption, audience members are able to create parasocial relationships with media personal in “real-life” soap operas. Since audience members seek parasocial relationships with people they can identify with, but they are more inclined or able to relate to non-celebrities at a higher degree than with celebrities because they see non celebrities more like themselves. (Giles, 2002). In India the cases are just opposite that celebrities attract more audiences than a non celebrities.

Reality shows are a popular and trendy genre for Indian television viewing audience since few decades which shows participants in situations testing their nerves, intelligence, sentiments, even body language and integrity. The camera catches all these responses and therefore looks totally natural. Candid camera in U.S catches the reaction of those people who didn't knew they are on camera but today's reality shows stand different and unique from those era and other television shows because the

responses that are believed to be supposedly unscripted. Reality Shows survive on human emotions, that play to an audience, for them its the only source of entertainment.

The appeals of reality television and audience interactions with cast members are similar to those of day time daily soap operas. For many decades, soap operas have been a popular and routine escapes for people facing boredom or the drama of their own lives. When introduced to television characters, audiences engage and get lost themselves in parasocial interactions common with real-life social interactions that can later turn into relationships (Perse & Rubin, 1998). reality television broke the monopoly and boredom of saas – bahu melodrama in India to create some interesting scripts and out of the world or out of the box ideas that made them stood apart from all the shows. Although there has been no change of taste or preference among drama-lovers as they are still glued to their television sets at prime time, but reality shows are hard hitting and gaining momentum, striving hard to come into the limelight in a large extent.

Although origins of this forms of reality television have been around since the 1940s, but the speed it took and the concept of watching “real” and original people act out their daily lives in front of the camera did not gain popularity until the early 1990s with the creation of MTV’s The Real World (Aslama & Pantti, 2006; Orbe, 2008; Ouellette & Murray, 2009). There are two things about reality shows that we should know which attracts viewers and then generate controversy: firstly the concept of reality or realism; and secondly the shock effect. The concept of reality TV draws its inspiration from reality shown in few cinema. So, you can say it's a format that portrays ordinary people as 'lively', supposedly no written screen play or dialogue or situations, and monitors and judges their emotions, their behaviour or their talent. Such formats usually invoke good tough competition and declares big money as rewards.

The success of the Indian reality shows came right after the success story of Kaun Banega Crorepati (2000), which was anchored by a bollywood celebrity and Indian legend Mr. Amitabh Bachchan. The success of this reality show opened up the Pandora box and numerous avenues for those types shows on Indian television sawal dus crore ka hosted by anupam kher and manisha koirala, jeeto chhapad phaad ke hosted by all favourite govinda. As advertisers were ready to invest and in india, there was no dearth of participants and undiscovered talents. In the pre-KBC era, reality television was limited to quiz programmes, chat shows, music-based countdown shows or game shows like saanph sidhi, antaakshiri, saare gama pa, the wheel of fortune, meri awaaz suno etc. but Indian broadcasters too realised that inorder to gain a space not only on television but also among Indian viewer’s heart, they roped in bollywood and television industry celebrities who were either famous or went into doom, but has a strong presence and followers.

“In The Image”, Daniel J. Boorstin (1961) states, that the celebrity are people who is known for his well-knownness. Anything that strikes the emotional quotient of Indian viewer is an instant hit in our country and bollywood celebrities are weakness of the viewers, they go to any extent to follow their celebrity The reason for this is that we Indians are high and value their emotional sentiments and every Indian (even the most straight face one) has an emotional side hidden somewhere. The success or main mantra or credibility of reality shows in India should be given to a certain extent to this weakness of Indian viewers. Apart from this, the plus point of these type of shows that it provides an alternatives apart from the saas-bahu soaps, which is still dominating television prime time space, is another reason for immense popularity of reality shows.

Reality television can allow an ordinary individual to become a celebrity in the blink of an eye. Horton and Wohl (1956) found interactions with non-fictitious persona or character television, such as quizmasters, create or develop a perception in the minds of audience members’ that the people who play themselves are real celebrities. The same phenomenon occurs with reality television. The craze for reality television hit India way before kaun banega crorepati, when channel V came up with a show called Viva, a band of five young singers. When channel V announced the auditions, young and dynamic dreamers gathered in huge numbers to give their luck a another chance. The audience find apathy with crying of contestants when they failed, audience also celebrated when contestants triumphed. The audience, on its part, lapped up and full of these overdose of emotions thrown at them by the channel. The show was a big success and an inspiration for both the shrewd business minds who want to invest in television industry and also for the young dreamers waiting for their share of luck and fame.

By the start of the new millennium, and with the success of the popular CBS program Survivor, major networks started using reality television programs as a tool to fill prime time viewing slots to gain audience attention. From 2009 to 2010, nine of the top 20 programs during primetime were reality-based television programs (Dehnart, 2010). And this type of adventure program spread like fire in many countries including India with new name “sarkar raj” In India too there has been no turning back as these reality television shows increased with each passing day and you see not nine out of twenty but atleast five reality shows in prime time slots occupied Indian minds. With the registration for every reality show surpassing the other one and the audience doing the votings that too not thousands, not even crores but in billions, at primitive stage people doubt the success of reality shows in longer run but seeing the record voting, all doubts over the acceptability by the Indian audience for these shows were cleared. The real life indian's came forward for the auditions of Indian Idol, Fame Gurukul, India's Best draamebaaj, Roadies, etc. Almost every channel today has their 'Abhijeet Sawant' of Indian idol and a 'Qazi' of Fame Gurukul to boast about.

Reality shows not only changed the stars of many television channels but also for many ordinary people, like Kunal Ganjawala, Sunidhi Chauhan, Shreya Ghosal and Anushka are some of the successful findings of talents from reality television. It was only from these shows that a tea shop owner, Sunil Pal, became a laughter champion and Prashant, a sepyo from Darjeeling, became the third Indian Idol, as an example. Hall (2009) found that when characters in a reality show appear authentic, viewers imagine themselves in the place of the cast member. Although viewers are aware that many of the scenarios on reality television are false, audiences are still able to engage with cast members and relate to their personal experiences of theirs. Furthermore, Hall (2009) finds that social and cognitive involvement are both strongly related to program and how people respond i.e. enjoyment Hall (2009) argues that people are still able to relate to them if their behaviour seems authentic. Hall (2009).

Celebrity reality shows are another aspect of reality television that has become extremely popular with the audience, and was created specifically by general entertainment channels to compete and for t.r.p's. Apart from the overwhelming Television Rating Points (TRPs) that these shows command, they also have their credit of revamping images of few celebrities and bringing back to limelight. some of the lost stars are item queen Rakhi Sawant witnessd a change after appearing on the reality show, Big Boss. names like Rahul Roy of film aashique fame, Anupama Verma a yeaster year model and Baba Sehgal, the first Indian rapper came to limelight again because of shows like bigg boss.

The viewers' feelings about the characters on the programs drive audiences' enjoyment from a television show. The writers and producers of television shows use common themes and narratives across different genres to allow the audience to make personal and moral judgments about characters with little personal knowledge about characters when viewers initially interact with a persona. audiences quickly decide if they like or dislike characters on a show. When audiences like a television character, they are able to relax the strict moral codes they apply to people in the real world for the sake of enjoyment. Gratifications through escapism, companionship, pleasure, and emotional connections further motivate viewers to remain morally disengaged with their favorite characters (Raney, 2004). GECs roll out big- ticket shows especially and that too during the festivals, when brands are very active and are ready to pay a premium. The idea of any reality show is to grab a bigger share of the ad pie or advertisement revenue. Reality shows and the Bollywood blockbusters have shown two sides of the same coin as many bollywood films are promoted through reality and then ride on star value. Most brands look to reality shows to get impact and a good launch and mileage for their campaign, which the fiction shows lack.

Unlike scripted shows, reality shows look for title and associate sponsors. According to industry standards the title sponsorship comes for Rs 10-15 crore and many times more than that if its attached with a celebrity hosting, judging or just a participants; while the associate sponsorship costs Rs 3-6 crore; and about six to eight associate sponsors are accommodated in a reality show. The 10-second ad-spot rates for a reality show are also bit slightly higher than the fiction shows, and fetch between Rs 1.5-4 lakh. Thus, reality shows earn between Rs 30-70 crore from sponsorships, besides another Rs 20 crore from other ads. However, often this amount is not enough to cover the investment on the show.

(source: business world edition January 2012).

Affectively oriented or otherwise para social responses are comprised of the viewer's feeling toward the persona of the character, both positive and negative. Just as we deal with our friends in the real world, it takes direct observation and evaluations of gestures, tone, and behaviours to determine if we like or dislike a persona or character (Horton & Wohl, 1956). Reality shows with celebrities acts linking thread and also as for viewers; it provides increased visibility and a chance to reach out to a larger TV-viewing audience. It presents greater chances and variability of the various channels which are being sampled by the not-so-loyal viewers, and provides good and greater opportunity for brand to integrate and product placements.

No wonder though, the star quotient in India is important as it not only attracts viewers instantly; but it also engages the audience with the show content that keeps viewers stick to these reality shows. After all, blockbuster movies featuring the biggest stars are always hit among Indian viewers and they bomb at the box office, similarly the reality shows which has a celebrity tag gets automatic recognition.

In reality television, when cast members directly address viewers in seemingly private face-to-face interactions, it allows the audience to be empathetic toward the character and develops more understanding toward their behaviour whether good or bad. According to Eyal and Fox (2007), identification by any individual is an affective process that allows audience members to adopt different perception for person and live by their experiences intensely. Within physical social relationships, they become loyal viewers or fans or devotees of their favourite person (celebrity) or character in the show, regardless of whether the character is fictional or real. Fans believe they know and understand the person in a reality show, the ways other do not and they believe they can anticipate what the person will say and do next. (Eyal & Fox, 2007). Ever since and way before, Indian television came into existence Indian audience had always idolised bollywood stars and looked up to them as a role model, it makes great logic that TV shows which uses celebrities as ambassadors to increase their viewership. As the television market space has now become very competitive and with so many reality TV shows and so many celebrities being a part of such shows it makes for a great research study. Keeping this in mind the purpose of this unit is to understand the impact of celebrities on the Indian reality shows and its audience.

Celebrity reality shows are the latest craze and in few years, a hit in the world of entertainment. They are also a great source of generating revenue and through them, various channels help themselves to raise their GRPS'. Indian audiences are known for being attracted by the charm of celebrities. They want to discover everything about them whether it is off-screen or on screen and celebrity reality shows present a more and personal human version of the stars.

Celebrity reality shows shows them in such a way that enable the audiences to relate with their favourite stars in a rather realistic manner. It is on these sets of the shows that they get to see a true and non-glamorised version of the stars. People trust celebrities and because of this trust they start believing in what is shown to them. They are excited to see the drama queens and kings of fiction Indian soaps, desi pop stars and models without make-up doing tantrums but striving hard to win the competitions.

Celebrities reflect consumer interest. with an actor like Salman Khan coming on board, a show' not only appeal hugh masses but also among classes, it clearly gets both sets of audiences. Stars attached with the reality shows definitely take the show to a different level and to a new heights, and will help to attract a newer set of audiences plus they also want to retain loyal audience and give them the gift of their loyalty by bringing celebrity on tv channels so that they do not switch on the remote control and a star like Salman khan is in position to hold the audience.

Reality shows with celebrities are just a reviving things for entertainment channels and act more like uplifting the brand image for the broadcaster and doing an association of the celebrity who has hugh fan following also gets attached with the brand. These celebrity based shows how ever don't deliver the kind of TRPs required for the channel, beyond a certain point.

So according to researchers, the reasons why a celebrities are introduced by channels and broad casters are

- 1) increase the trp or usp of the channel.
- 2) connect with the huge fan following of celebrity.
- 3) attract advertisers and sponsors for the show
- 4) as to make reality show a brand among viewers.

Verma and Larson (2002) in their study found that those adolescents who watch television for approximately 12 hour per week on an average goes through stress relieving activity. It was concluded in the study that 29% of viewers watch television for purpose of learning/education. Verma and Larson (2002). Celebrity based shows mostly help the channel carve a niche or branding image among established players and keep the audience engaged through such shows. Programs as such draw a large number of first time audiences to the channels. It is used like a burst programming vehicle that attracts many eyes of the competitors.

Channels like Colors started its journey with big-budget reality shows like Big Boss, hosted by salmaan khan and sanjay dutt in the last season, and Khatron Ke Khiladi with Akshay Kumar as the host in first two seasons, it was done to get into the eyes of viewers who were also good loyal fans of celebrities and this loyalty was passed from celebrities to channels and thus were able to make themselves a brand too, so simple. Just to grab a eyeball both celebrities were used as marketing vehicles for the channel. Fatima (2000) suggests through research that TV has a long-term effect on people's thinking. Therefore, instead of glamorization, portrayal of crime and commercialization, positive trends need to be introduced on the TV channels in order to save our values. Fatima (2000)

Bukhari (2002) concludes that the youth is getting out of orthodox and hence advancing to new ideas regarding the placement and position of women in the society. Bukhari (2002)

Parasocial relationships are one sided relationships that audience members develop over repeated interactions with their favorite personae in the media. Soap opera fans are most attracted to characters which whom they are able to identify and perceive as real and authentic. The serial nature of documentary soap operas on reality television provides similar para social relationships with their viewers. Just as fans of daytime soap operas have vicariously lived through those characters, fans on reality television now do the same with documentary soap operas on shows such as Gene Simmon's Family Jewels and Keeping with the Kardashians. Most reality shows allow audiences to follow the lives of reality characters from week to week. For example, fans watch as contestants compete twice a week on the X Factor to win a singing contract, as the cast of Jersey Shore lives together over numerous seasons in different cities and countries, and as overweight contestants fight to lose weight on The Biggest Loser. Reality television provides an opportunity for audiences to interact with "real" people, acting their lives out in front of the camera, allowing the show to resemble a real-life soap opera. The storylines in daytime soap operas, however, are the creation of writers, whereas, in reality television, the stories (for the most part) evolve unpredictably during the filming of the show (Perse & Rubin, 1990). Similarly shows like Dus Ka Dum, hosted by actor Salman Khan on Sony Entertainment Pvt Ltd has been able to clinch viewership for the channels. And biggest loser kaun hosted by suniel shetty, the star power and the interactivity content of the game show made it more appealing to the masses. The show recorded good Television Rating Points (TRPs) and provided the channel a new breath of fresh air as it was needed in the competition. Giacomo Corneo (2002) found out in his research that in OECD countries watching television is by far the most time-consuming and entertaining form of leisure activity. Surprisingly, many researchers feel television viewing is positively and directly correlated with working hours across many countries. Workers and capitalists are shown to exhibit opposite preference orderings over equilibria. (Giacomo Corneo (2002))

Another strategy is to have mix of non-celebrity and celebrity in a reality shows, which make good business sense. like Dance India Dance had a celebrity judge as Mithun Chakraborty, the participants came from ordinary and humble backgrounds. The show did good business for them because advertisers too liked the format. Ahluwalia and Singh (2011) found in their study that on an average, children watch two hours or less of TV daily and most of them indulged during bedtime TV Viewing. They watched TV only for entertainment and for learning and gaining knowledge from dance reality shows. Childrens' most preferred programs that exactly was tagged as "childrens" shows/serials, followed by cartoon/animated programs. Ahluwalia and Singh (2011).

Uses of celebrities in a reality shows: (Sharma.s 2014)

- 1) **Establishes Credibility:** a reality show done by a celebrity fosters a sense of trust for that show and channel among the target audience. This is especially true in of new shows. The role of a celebrity in a reality show is, without doubt, linked to the reputation the celebrity. : Amitabh bachhan for Kbc, Amir khan for Satyamev jayte, salman khan for big boss. In brief people relate personal identification, and they develop sympathy, or emotional attachments for characters they admire by putting themselves in the place of those characters and imagining how they would perform and respond in similar situations (Eberson & Woods, 2007, p. 33).
- 2) **Attracts attentions through controversies attached with celebrities:** Unnikrishnan and Bajpai (1996) found in their study that about 48% upper class and 62% middle-class Indians watch Television for more than two hours per everyday. Unnikrishnan and Bajpai (1996) and it is result of celebrities who ensures attention of the target group by breaking the clutter of varieties of different genres running on the channels and making the show a brand and more noticeable. Example. On an episode of “Rakhi Ka Insaaf” or “Rakhi Is Judge,” some young, aspiring Bollywood actresses threw slippers at a producer they said had demanded casting couch favors. Another contestant committed suicide, his relatives claim, after the hostess of the show publicly called him impotent.
- 3) **Associative Benefit:** A celebrity’s preference for a reality show sends out a strong message that it is being liked by celebrity therefore consumer will also benefit. the behaviorally oriented parasocial responses are comprised of the viewer’s verbal, non-verbal, and para social communication responses to the person during interactions. Viewers can then become active participants in the media exposure by responding verbally and non-verbally to the persona of celebrities (Schramm & Hartmann, 2008)
- 4) **Demographic connects:** Different celebrity stars appeal differently to various demographic segments (age, gender, class, geography etc) and also establishes them in the minds of international audiences.
- 5) **Mass appeal:** Some stars have a universal appeal and therefore prove to be a good bet to generate interest among the masses.
- 6) **Psychographic Connect:** celebrities are loved and worshipped by their fans therefore producers and channels use these stars to capitalize on these feelings to attract the fans towards their reality shows. Behavioral responses have become increasingly and most active in the age and era of Internet and news and electronic media. Although the relationship is one-sided in that it is not a direct and impact conversation, audiences begin to feel involved that they invested in the relationship with the people on their favorite shows and begin to care about them and want to know what happens next. The Internet assists with the fascination of television shows because viewers can go on those blogs or log in into websites to find out more about cast members even before the next episode premieres. (Horton & Wohl, 1956),
- 7) **Rejuvenating a stagnant brand:** with the objective of infusing fresh lease of life into the stagnant shows or channels, they rope in celebrities to revive the trps or usp of their channels or product. Example On “Swayamvar 2” (an adaptation of Swayamvara, an ancient practice of competition for a royal woman’s hand), women competed to marry Rahul Mahajan, a divorced politician’s son who had been arrested on charges of drug possession. One contestant, a women’s rights activist, did a sultry cage dance to woo him. The winner, a model, separated from him four months after their marriage and accused him of domestic violence.
- 8) **Mitigating a tarnished image :** due to huge competition from many channels and their products like daily serials, music, adventure, cartoon, wildlife etc, some times channels phase out their loyal fans and indirectly sponsors too which results in suffering of losses and sending a message to the people that the channel is not performing well and providing innovative and creative content to the viewers, this indicates their tarnished image, in order to get back and attract those lost customers, these channels take the help of real stories like reality shows.

9) The F.R.E.D principle: this principle helps in relating the factors common between reality shows, celebrity, and consumers.

- 1) F is for familiarity. The Target market must be aware of the celebrity and see him as an empathetic, credible, sincere and trustworthy.
- 2) R is for Relevance.. There should be a meaningful link between the reality shows and the celebrity as a host or a judge or as a participant. If the consumers identify the link then the consumer feels more free to accept the content, buy the product advertised during the reality shows, and make the show face the competition more easily.
- 3) E is for Esteem. Consumers must have the utmost respect and confidence for the celebrity. Like Amitabh Bachchan for KBC, Priyanka Chopra for Guinness Book of World Record, Salman Khan for Big Boss and Dus Ka Dum etc.
- 4) D is for differentiation: The target consumers must see the reality show celebrity as a cut above the rest. This means the audience should be in a position to differentiate different reality shows with their concept and it could be only possible through identification of celebrity by the audience.

Advantage for broadcaster for introducing celebrity or associating a celebrity with the reality show.

1. A celebrity can enhance brand equity of not only the show but to the whole image of the company. (Till, 1998)
2. Consumer's behaviour can be altered or change or make a good positive effect on viewers. (Till, 1998)
3. Celebrity can add new dimension to a brand or product which can contribute to the revenue of the show. (Till, 1998)
4. Culture as a road can be used for your own good, in other words it can be manipulated by celebrity who has huge fan following. (Kaikati, 1987).
5. Celebrity creates credibility for the brand or product or shows in a short period of time. i.e. quick and successive response from the viewers. (Abbot et al., 2001). Not only that celebrity appearing in an advertising or reality show, builds whole and sole credibility for the product. (Mullikin and Petty (2006)).
6. A world-reputed celebrity helps any advertisements (reality shows) look different or makes it stand out from clutters of competitive products. (Atkin and Block, 1983).
7. The broad casters believe that consumer will follow or buy product associated with their celebrity whom they trust, admire and respect. (Wright, 2000)
8. The broadcaster will have competitive advantage when they rope in a celebrity to endorse a product or shows. (Wright, 2000).
9. Celebrity makes any thing believable whether it is a product or any shows. (Kamins, 1989)
10. The broad casters get a brand recognition when they associate themselves with a celebrity. (Petty, Cacioppo, Schermann, 1983)
11. Influence consumers or viewer's perception or intention. (Tripp, Jensen, Carlson, 1994).
12. Broadcasters product or show gets an individual personality. (McCracken, 1989).

Disadvantage of using celebrity in a reality shows:

- 1. Consumer not ready to believe:** many viewers or consumer will not believe that the celebrity himself or herself giving importance to the product or shows. (Hsu and McDonald, 2002).
- 2. Vampire effect:** when a celebrity is too attractive or popular, it will have his/her fans following them but once they are replaced, audiences too disperse. (Rossiter and Percy, 1997)
- 3. Wrong fit:** when a product or shows gets a wrong mismatch celebrity then too broadcast can suffer. (Till and Shimp, 1998)

Effectiveness of a celebrity reality shows:

Reality shows seem to have gripped the imagination and thinking of the nation. It is catering to the voyeuristic or the creative needs of the TV audiences. The channels are really obsessed with their TRPs and they go any extent to provide real things in their reality shows.

Reality-based television programs may be prone to parasocial relationships because cast members reveal raw emotions to the audience during the shows' face-to-face interactions with the camera (Ebersole & Woods, 2007). reality shows like Indian Idol, India's got talent, Sa Re Ga Ma Pa and Star Voice of India are truly energetic for the audience. They have double magnetic effect on the audience and become topics of day conversations whether at dinner tables, college canteens or lunch hours. The reality shows focus on discovering and nurturing the hidden talent from various corners of India and transform the deserving candidates into professional ones that is providing industry experience.

A celebrity is made by all of viewers who willingly read about him, who like to see him on television, who buy recordings of his voice, and talk about him to our friends. Boon, S. D., & Lomore, C.D. (2001). The effect of these celebrity reality shows is barely over that the audience is in the hand of or grip of celebrity reality shows like Nach Baliye and Jhalak Dikhlaja or fear factor. every body knows these reality shows seems to be only a publicity gimmick cashing upon the celebrities participating in them. The question arises that does it mean that the respective channels adopts to host the so-called celebrity reality shows are deceiving the audience just to boost their TRP ratings and generate publicity for the characters participating in them?

According to researcher (turner, 2005) celebrity reality shows are the latest craze in the world of entertainment. They are also a great means of generating revenue plus help the channels to raise their TRP ratings. Indian audiences are known for being hypnotized by the charm of celebrities. They want to discover everything about celebrity whether it is off-screen or onscreen and celebrity reality shows present a more human version of the stars. People follow the lives of celebrities from gossip, tabloid magazines, online websites, social media, and on reality television. Even if just as a surveillance tool, some people watch reality television shows with celebrities to know what is going on in their lives, even if they find the material morally offensive. Audiences that watch reality television programs have come to expect conflict, sexual adventure, and the pleasure of voyeurism when they consume these programs (Turner, 2005)

Many researchers contradict that there is anything so real about any celebrity reality shows. It is just a revenue generating trick for the various television channels. All these people performing in reality shows are celebrities and they are definitely doing this for money. There cannot be a comparison between reality talent hunt shows like Indian Idol, Sa Re Ga Ma Pa, Star Voice of India and celebrity reality shows like coffee with karan, comedy night with kapil etc. as those platforms are meant for discovering new talent which is genuine and celebrity reality shows are just fake. But shows like Survivor took the idea of having strangers live and work together from The Real World and turned the contrived situation into a competitive game show that spanned over the course of months. The suspense of reality game shows proved to be very enjoyable for viewers. Competitive reality shows, for example, range from programs with formats from the soap opera appeals of Survivor to the talent-based shows of American Idol, and dating or romance shows, such as The Bachelor. There are also celebrity versions of these competitive reality programs like Celebrity Apprentice, Dancing with the Stars, and Celebrity Fit Club. (Nabi et al., 2006). And made people believe that these celebrities support real content. In India too these foreign format were adopted and showed with celebrity connect and thus the audience was attracted to the show believing it to be true. Reality show like The Real World allowed audiences to watch "real" people act out their daily lives in front of the camera in ways never before on television. Expanding on the idea of The American Family, MTV conceptualized the idea of putting eight strangers in a house together and having their intimate lives at home and work filmed for several months..Audiences were to witness to all the drama, sex, and conflict of the cast members (Ouellette & Murray, 2009).

Although some "celebrealty" shows can increase a celebrity's fame, these shows allow audiences to get to know them in an unscripted manner that humanizes them. (Stelter, 2009). Indian celebrity reality shows enable the audiences to relate with the stars in a rather realistic manner. It is on the sets of these shows that they get to see a non-glamourised version of the stars. People start believing in what is shown to them. They are happy to see the drama queens and kings of popular Indian soaps, desi pop stars and models without make-up and striving to win a competition. But what stands out is the fact that how real is all the back-stage drama depicted on-screen? Where do these shows stand in front of reality talent hunt shows and what makes the audience fall for them. People in india are awed by celebrities. "What turns them on is the fact that celebrities are as human as all of us and this is what makes the celebrity reality shows click. Brand celebrities always click with the audience and television channels know exactly how to cash upon their image.(Jessica evans, david.h,2005)

Some researcher believes that everybody is in the aura of reality shows these years. It is a fact that if any celebrity associate his or her name with reality shows then that attachment to any of those shows, it is going to take off. Even reality talent hunt shows would have struggled and could not have done so well without celebrity judges. as India is a star-struck nation. People are always eager to know what's happening in the lives and that too personal lives of the stars. Celebrity reality shows might be a publicity stunt but it has helped the viewers to relate with the stars. (Jessica evans, david.h,2005) (Hamish pringle, 2004).

Researchers believe that not all reality shows are bad but shows like Indian Idol, india's got talent, dance India dance etc are a great platform for discovering or unearthing hidden talent. the curiosity among viewers and the desire to participate in the final judgment gets them glued to the show. In celebrity reality shows too, the audience feel they can help their favourite stars win through public votes.

Many researchers even feel that celebrity reality shows are dumb gimmicks that clearly make fool of the audience. No doubt they are good in increasing the TRP ratings of various channels and increasing the revenue of Telecom companies. The shows seem to have tie-ups with all major telecom companies and help them generate revenue as well. the poor people who end up voting for their favourite stars doesn't even realise that they are being bluffed.

It is not as if the Indian audience is not aware about the difference between celebrity reality shows and talent hunt shows in fact they feel that celebrity reality shows should not be given the same weightage as talent hunt shows but they are not a medium to fool people. Somewhere researchers agree that celebrities are participating in these shows from all walks of life but then they also have to face tough competition from each other. They are also human at the same time. They say that these shows are not entirely cooked or made-up but also have some shades of reality prospects. (Dubrofsky & Hardy, 2008) reveals that the interesting dynamic of reality television is that it not only gives the ordinary person fame, but it also allows celebrities to become ordinary. Reality television allows audiences to watch the lives of celebrities in their everyday routines. VH1 began to explore reality-based television featuring celebrities with *The Surreal Life*. One of the original cast members, former Public Enemy member Flavor Flav, went on to star in four additional VH1 reality television shows (*Strange Love with Bridgitte Neilson* and three seasons of *Flavor of Love*), which spawned three spinoffs (*I Love New York*, *Charm School*, and *Rock of Love* featuring Poison front man Brett Michaels) Since, VH1 has branded an entire block of programming featuring celebrities on its reality shows known as "celebrity" (Orbe, 2008).

Audience members can also interact with their favourite reality-based programs researching information about upcoming episodes and cast members on the Internet. Many reality-based television programs have become popular for features that span across different sub-genres. Audience members are able to actively engage while watching reality television because of its interactive features. Holmes (2004) found this format empowers the audience to have a participatory role on the reality show by voting by phone, Internet or text for its favorite contestant. The audience can directly affect the outcomes of competitive reality programs such as *American Idol* by calling in to vote. On VH1 dating shows such as the last season of *Flavor of Love* and *Megan Wants a Millionaire*, viewers were able to vote online for which contestants would make the first round of potential love interests for the celebrity. Holmes (2004) These reality-based programs function as social interactions because audience members tend to discuss cast members and possible outcomes of the contestant with peers. Social involvement heightens the authenticity of a cast member. Hall (2009) found that audiences who view reality television spend a lot of time talking about cast members with friends whether they are celebrities or non celebrity. Audience members further engage in an active role with reality-based programs. by opinions posted online and through blogs. Hall (2009) Beyond filling various needs and gratifications, reality television also influences cultural identity. According to Turner (2005), Youth audiences are high consumers of celebrity, and celebrity is now a standard by-product of the promotion of the [reality] TV [documentary] soap opera. Audiences expect conflict, sexual adventure and the pleasure of voyeurism when they consume reality television (Turner, 2005). The voyeuristic appeal of reality television and the innate curiosity of human nature have made these types of programs fill a gratifying need fictional television could not (Nabi et al. 2006). The voyeuristic nature of reality television can also satisfy guilty desires. Audiences get to see "real" people on reality based television engage in naughty behaviour designed to make us feel guilty about our enjoyment while watching (Ebersole & Woods, 2007). These soap characters frequently reminded viewers of people they knew, and viewers used characters' situations and behaviours as ways of understanding their own lives," Giles (2002,). Some reality-based shows allow cast members to break the privacy wall of theirs with viewers by speaking directly to the audience about their experiences in a confessional booth (Aslama & Pantti, 2006).

Celebrity reality shows are not only is a mode of entertainment or source of entertainment but are also backed with many controversies which target the emotions of the audience. If you see your favourite star dancing with a broken foot or back-pain or sickness, you are compelled to vote for him or her. Moreover, these shows stars appealing for votes as if viewers votes are important for them and the competition means the world to them. Many stars go to any extent , in the past have done whatever they could to win these competitions.

Celebrity reality television shows not only helps television industry flourish but also helps the other business like restaurants like I personally visit McDonald's and pizza hut or dinning restaurants, there I find l.c.d on with reality shows going on and customers are glued to shows like India's got talent, Indian idol etc.

celebrity reality shows are getting popular in India because audiences feel firstly celebrities are role models .second programming time and schedules of the show does matter for an audience comfortability. Third, friends circles are biggest boost and informal mouth to mouth viral marketing for reality shows. fourth marketing and advertising is done on huge scale for reality shows through

- 1) newspaper
- 2) hoardings
- 3) TV
- 4) friends or relatives
- 5) social networking sites like face book and twitter.
- 6) sms/ mobile phone

.and fifth some where celebrity create comfort level for the family that is make a family show.

Therefore effectiveness of Reality shows seem to be the new age entertainment recipe. They might be selling controversies or cashing upon people's emotions, but at the end of the day they are popular shows with an ever-growing TRP rating.

influence on people after watching celebrity reality shows:

case study of satyamev jayte (hosted by actor aamir khan). episode of alchohol consumption and its effects.

(sources: official website of satyamev jayte)

Responses= 751487					Donations =3983002		
Comments	Activity	Tweets	Sms	ivr	Online	Via	Reliance
On	on		votes		donation	Sms	Foundation
websites	face book				1850263	141238	1991501
9.98%	68.53%	4.57%	16.6%	0.32%			

connections	751487
1. Website	085%
2. facebook	47.96%
3. youtube	1.56%
4. twitter	49.49%
5. mobile	1.14%

Community members	421054
1. Web site	56.27%
2. facebook	29.22%
3. mobile	9.33%
4. twitter	5.14%

There were 69% male, and 31% female

Age ratio in maximum order:

- 1) Age between 23-34
- 2) Age between 18-22
- 3) Age between 35-60
- 4) Age between 60 +

Top three cities: 1) New Delhi

2) Mumbai

3) Kolkatta

Top three countries: 1) India

2) Singapore

3) U.a.e.

The General Service Office (GSO) of Alcoholics Anonymous (AA) India, which operates from a tiny municipal school in Byculla, was bursting at its seams as nearly 100 AA members and volunteers attended to a torrent of calls after a national TV show flashed AA's helpline numbers and website details, on Sunday.

In its ninth episode which first aired at 11am, *Satyamev Jayate* focused on alcoholism and featured interviews with experts and recovering alcoholics, including AA member Laxman. As the show's producer and host Aamir Khan announced the number on air, AA offices across the country braced themselves.

Gajanan Rotated trustee of AA India who was at the AA office in Mumbai said The number was first flashed on the show at 11 37am and at 11 40am we received the first call Within 20 minutes the AA website had crashed At 12 30am all telephone lines were jammed and missed calls started piling up Within the next hour we received 8 600 missed calls By 4pm AA centers across India had received 13 000 calls which jumped up to 28 000 by 7 in the evening after the show aired At the time of going to print More than 31 000 calls were recorded Alcoholics.

(sources: DNA newspaper dated 2nd july 2012)..

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES OF DATA COLLECTION:

98 VIEWERS WERE INTERVIEWED BASED ON QUESTIONNAIRE METHOD AND DATA WERE COLLECTED ON THIS.(AGE GROUP: 14-30)

MEN	49
WOMEN	49

1. how often you watch television.(please tick)

- 1) **always**
- 2) **most often**
- 3) **sometimes**
- 4) **very rare**

2. how much hours you spent on watching television.

- 1) **less than one hour**
- 2) **1-3 hours**
- 3) **3-5 hours**
- 4) **more than 5 hours**

Valaskakis Lowery and DeFleur (1988) showed in their research that children or youth tend to watch more television than do adults, prefer to watch adult programs, and usually watch as late into the night as do adults. Despite their emergence from the more limited world of childhood and their increased reliance on peers, adolescents continue to spend a great deal of their time watching television

3. what is the like of television programs. (tick best four)

4. Are you a frequent viewer of reality show.

yes	26
no	29
sometimes	43

5. what genre of celebrity reality show you would love to watch. (any one)

1)	celebrity as a judge	18
2)	celebrity as a participants	55
3)	celebrity as a anchor	25

6. which channel shows best celebrity reality shows?(only one)

1)	sony	21
2)	star plus	21
3)	zee tv	12
4)	colors	28
5)	any other channel (mention)	16

7. why are celebrity reality shows popular in india?(any one)

1)	celebrities are role models .	33
2)	because of time and schedules of the show.	11

- 3) **friends suggest each other.** 15
- 4) **marketing and advetising is done on huge scale.** 29
- 5) **celebrity create comfort level for the family.** 10

8. celebrity v/s non celebrity reality show

Less popular celebrity in a reality show

Roadies	28
Emotional attyachhar	12
Rakhi ka swayamvar	00
Crime petrol	50
Big switch	01
Master chef	15

More popular Celebrity in a reality show.

Big boss	43
Dance india dance	37
Indian idol	10
India's got talent	23
Sa re ga ma	06
Kbc	41
Jhalak	19
Nach baliye	18
Coffee with karan	03
Satya mev jayte	19
Sachh ka saamna	01
Khatron ke khilaadi	14
X factor	07
Boogie woogie	04
Kya aap paanchvi class se tezz hai	01

10. what influence you more in a celebrity reality shows. any one

- 1) his sense of humour 45**
- 2) his down to earth nature. 14**
- 3) his attire/clothing. 16**
- 4) his marketing style. 23**

11. where do you get information about your celebrity reality shows(tick one).

- 1) newspaper 23**
- 2) hoardings 03**
- 3) tv 55**
- 4) friends or realatives 08**
- 5) social networking sites 09**
like facebook and twitter.
- 6) sms/ mobile phone 00**

12. **what is the after- effect of watching favourite celebrity reality show. (tick only three)**
- 1) **purchase or watch any thing what ever my celebrity endorses.**
15
 - 2) **will discuss the show with my friends.** 80
 - 3) **will gather more information on my celebrity.**
31
 - 4) **if missed the show, eagerness to watch highlights.**
42
 - 5) **will watch all favourite episode of this reality show on youtube.**
23
 - 6) **will even watch or gather information about other reality shows done by my celebrity.**
23

13. what according to you, celebrity is taken in a reality show to,

- 1) increase the trp or usp of the channel. 50
- 2) connect with the huge fan following of celebrity. 16
- 3) attract advertisers and sponsors for the show. 14
- 4) as to make reality show a brand among viewers. 18

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